

AWARENESS OF DIABETIC RETINOPATHY IN TYPE 2 DIABETES MELLITUS PATIENTS

FIRST AUTHOR: Dr. Kotha Prasanna, Assistant Professor, Department of community medicine, Konaseema Institute of Medical Sciences & Research Foundation, Amalapuram, Andhra Pradesh.

SECOND AUTHOR & CORRESPONDING AUTHOR: Dr. Renu Vasant Sulakhe, HOD & Professor, Department of community.

Background: Globally, type II diabetes mellitus is a serious public health issue. Diabetic retinopathy cannot be avoided, but its potentially blinding consequences can be reduced by educating those who have the condition. This study aims to assess the level of awareness about diabetic retinopathy among Type 2 diabetes patients and identify the factors influencing their understanding of the condition.

Methodology: A cross-sectional study was conducted among 78 patients of Type 2 Diabetes Patients >45 Years old in out Patient of PHC Bandarulanka, PHC Ambajipeta, CHC P.Gannavaram. Using a pre-made, semi-structured questionnaire, Google Forms was used to collect study data. The statistical analysis was conducted using SPSS software, version 2020.

Results: This study found that the majority of participants were aged 55-65 years (31%), with a nearly equal gender distribution (males 44%, females 34%). Most were illiterate (32%), followed by those with elementary education (23%). (71.8%) were aware the connection between diabetes and diabetes retinopathy, and 79.3% understand that diabetes can cause blindness. but only 48.7% had an eye checkup in the past year. Awareness levels were significantly influenced by age ($p=0.02$), with the 45-55 age group having the highest awareness (84.61%). Education also played a key role ($p=0.04$), with awareness rising from 43.75% among illiterates to 100% among university graduates.

Conclusion: The study reveals a knowledge gap in diabetic retinopathy awareness, especially regarding screening guidelines. Age and education impact awareness, highlighting the need for targeted education. Despite recognizing DR's impact and preventability, misconceptions about screening persist. Efforts should focus on promoting regular checkups, particularly for older and less-educated individuals.

Key words: Diabetic Retinopathy, Screening, Awareness

Introduction

Diabetes Mellitus (DM), a chronic metabolic disorder characterized by impaired glucose utilization due to insulin deficiency or imbalance. Among the numerous complications associated with DM, diabetic retinopathy (DR) is a significant cause of blindness worldwide, particularly among working-age adults.¹ Diabetic retinopathy (DR) is a serious complication of DM, which damages the capillaries and nerves of the eyesight due to uncontrolled blood glucose. The risk of developing DR increases over time as it occurs in approximately 77% of diabetic cases after 10 years of DM onset and reaches 100% after 30 years.²

Diabetic retinopathy is a significant complication of diabetes. It is deemed a leading cause of preventable blindness in working-age adults. According to the Global Burden of Disease Study, DR is the fifth leading cause of blindness in adults aged 50 years or older. Globally, the prevalence of DR among diabetic patients is estimated to be around 34%.³

The major risk factors that accelerate the development and progression of DR include high blood glucose, long-standing DM, and high blood pressure. Therefore, adequate lifelong control of glucose levels delays and reduces the progression of DR. Early detection and proper intervention could be enhanced through sufficient awareness and appropriate knowledge regarding such a highly prevalent disease.⁴

MATERIALS AND METHODS

- STUDY DESIGN: Cross-sectional study
- STUDY PARTICIPANTS: Type 2 Diabetes Patients >45 Years old
- STUDY SETTING: Out Patient of PHC Bandarulanka, PHC Ambajipeta, CHC P.Gannavaram
- SAMPLE TECHNIQUES: Convenient sampling
- INCLUSION CRITERIA: Type 2 Diabetes patients >45 years old
- EXCLUSION CRITERIA:

1. Type 2 Diabetes patients <45 years old,

2. Patients not willing to give consent,

3. Psychiatric patients and Unconscious patients

- **DATA COLLECTION PROCEDURE:** After getting informed consent from the participants, data was collected in a face to face interview using a predesigned, semi structured questionnaire.

- **CONFIDENTIALITY:** Particulars and details of all the participants were kept confidential throughout the study; only summary of the details was used for declaring the result

- **ETHICAL CONSIDERATION:** Institutional ethics committee approval was taken and informed consent was obtained.

- **DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION:** Data was entered using Microsoft Excel sheet. Summarisation and analysis of data was carried out by using IBM SPSS Software version 20(licensed). Descriptive Statistics: Mean, Percentage and Standard Deviation.

RESULTS

Table: 1 Demographic details of study participants

Parameters	Frequency	Percentage (%)
AGE		
45-55 Years	26	26
55-65 Years	31	31
>65 Years	21	21
SEX		
MALE	44	44
FEMALE	34	34
EDUCATION		

Illiterate	32	32
Elementary	23	23
High school	12	12
College	9	9
University	2	2
History with Diabetes		
<5 years	36	36
5-10 years	25	25
>10 years	17	17
Type of Medication		
Tablet	55	55
Insulin	8	8
Both	15	15

The majority study participants were between age group of 55-65 years (31%), followed by 45-55 years (26%) and those above 65 years (21%). Males (44%) and females (34%). Education levels vary, with the majority being illiterate (32%), followed by elementary (23%), high school (12%), college (9%), and university (2%). Most of the participants had diabetes for less than 5 years i.e, (36%), while 25% have had it for 5-10 years, and 17% for over 10 years. Treatment-wise, tablets are used by most (55%), while 8% rely on insulin, and 15% take both tablet and insulin therapy.

Table: 2 "Awareness and Perceptions of Diabetic Retinopathy on study participants

No.	Question	Correct Answer	% Correct Answers
1	Do you think there is a relationship between Diabetic retinopathy and DM?	Yes	71.8%
2	Do you think diabetes mellitus may lead to blindness?	Yes	79.3%
3	Have your eyes been checked by a doctor last year?	Yes	48.7%
4	Do you think good control of diabetes might prevent DR?	Yes	88.5%
5	Can a diabetic patient have eye problems at the same time as a diabetes diagnosis?	Yes	62.3%
6	How frequently should a person with diabetes undergo an eye checkup?	Yearly or every 2 years	24.4%
7	When you have diabetes for the first time, when must you screen your eye?	At the time of diagnosis	38.5%
8	Do you think retinopathy is a treatable condition?	Yes	92.3%
9	Do you think seeing an optometrist (regular eyeglass store) is enough for people with diabetes?	No	17.9%
10	No need for a regular screening for DR if both eyes are good?	No	23.1%

Most of participants, i.e, (71.8%) recognize the connection between diabetes and diabetes retinopathy, and 79.3% understand that diabetes can cause blindness. but only 48.7% had an eye checkup in the past year. Most participants (88.5%) believing that diabetes retinopathy can be avoided with proper diabetes management. but only 62.3% are aware

that eye problems can appear at diagnosis. Only 24.4% of people are aware of the required frequency of eye exams, and only 38.5% are aware of the necessity of screening upon diagnosis, indicating a low level of awareness of screening standards. Encouragingly, 92.3% believe DR is curable. However, misconceptions persist, as only 17.9% recognize that seeing an optometrist alone is insufficient, and only 23.1% disagree that routine screening is not required if eyesight is good.

Table: 3 showing Association between demographic Factors and awareness of diabetic retinopathy among study participants

Category	Aware (%)	Unaware (%)	p-value
AGE			
45-55 Years	84.61	15.39	
55-65 Years	51.61	48.39	0.02*
>65 Years	52.38	47.62	
SEX			
MALE	63.63	36.37	0.86
FEMALE	61.76	38.24	
EDUCATION			
Illiterate	43.75	56.25	
Elementary	69.56	30.44	0.04*
High school	75	25	
College	88.88	11.12	
University	100	0	
History with Diabetes			
<5 years	69.44	30.56	
5-10 years	68	32	0.1
>10 years	41.17	58.83	

Type of Medication			
Tablet	67.27	32.73	
Insulin	75	25	0.1
Both	40	60	

Age significantly influenced awareness, with the 45-55 age group showing the highest awareness (84.61%) compared to the 55-65 (51.61%) and >65 (52.38%) groups ($p=0.02$). Gender did not show a significant difference in awareness ($p=0.86$). Education played a crucial role, as awareness increased with higher education levels, from 43.75% among illiterates to 100% among university graduates ($p=0.04$). Diabetes duration and type of medication were not significantly associated with awareness, though those with diabetes for over 10 years (41.17%) and those using both tablets and insulin (40%) had lower awareness compared to others.

DISCUSSION

The present study revealed that 71.8% of participants were aware of the connection between diabetes and diabetic retinopathy (DR). In comparison, a study by P. K. Rani et al.¹ reported that only 49.9% of participants had knowledge of diabetes mellitus (DM), and 37.1% were aware of DR. Conversely, a study conducted by Aldahlawi A. et al.⁵ found a significantly higher awareness level, with 93% of participants recognizing that diabetes could affect their eyes. These variations in awareness levels across studies highlight the influence of regional differences, healthcare accessibility, and the effectiveness of diabetes education programs. The findings emphasize the need for continuous public health efforts to improve awareness of DR and encourage regular eye screenings for individuals with diabetes. Similar to previous research conducted in Saudi Arabia in Hail and in Al Jouf and Jeddah, in which 76% and 83% of patients were aware of DM's effect on the eyes respectively Regional studies in Oman.⁶, Jordan.⁷, and Turkey.⁸, also showed that a high percentage of patients were aware that DM could affect the eyes (93%, 88%, and 88%, respectively).

Most participants (88.5%) believed that diabetic retinopathy (DR) could be prevented with proper diabetes management. However, only 62.3% were aware that eye complications could be present at the time of diabetes diagnosis. Regarding practice patterns, P. K. Rani et al.¹ reported that among individuals with knowledge about DR, only 36.5% believed that maintaining good blood sugar control could eliminate the need for an ophthalmologist visit. In contrast, 55.5% of those without prior knowledge of DR held this belief, highlighting a significant misconception ($p < 0.0001$).

The present study reveals that only 24.4% of participants believe that eye checkups should be conducted every two years instead of yearly. This finding indicates a significant preference for more frequent eye examinations among the population. Comparing these results with the study conducted by Aldahlawi et al.⁵, a different distribution of opinions is observed. In their study, the majority (43%) believed that eye checkups should be done every six months, 39% preferred yearly checkups, 18% sought eye examinations only when vision was affected, and none selected the two-year interval.

Present study showed that, Age significantly influenced awareness, with the 45-55 age group showing the highest awareness (84.61%) compared to the 55-65 (51.61%) and >65 (52.38%) groups ($p = 0.02$). and Education played a crucial role, as awareness increased with higher education levels, from 43.75% among illiterates to 100% among university graduates ($p = 0.04$). Interestingly, individuals with <5 years of diabetes had greater DR knowledge than those with >10 years. In contrast to this study, Albadrani M S, et al.⁹ showed that, Patients with a longer duration of the disease (>10 years) were more likely to have a good level of knowledge about DR than those with a disease duration of five years or less (51.9% vs. 29.9%, $p = 0.006$). Patients diagnosed at a younger age were more likely to have good knowledge about DR than those diagnosed at an older age. These findings emphasize the need for targeted DR awareness programs, especially for older and less-educated individuals.

Conclusion

The study highlights that while a majority of participants recognize the link between diabetes and diabetic retinopathy (DR), gaps remain in awareness regarding screening guidelines and the necessity of regular eye checkups. Factors such as age and education significantly influenced awareness levels, with younger and more educated individuals demonstrating higher knowledge. Despite the belief that proper diabetes management can prevent DR, misconceptions persist regarding the role of optometrists and the frequency of screenings. These findings underscore the urgent need for targeted educational interventions to enhance awareness, particularly among older, less-educated individuals, and those with a longer history of diabetes, to promote timely screening and prevent vision-related complications.

REFERENCES

1. Rani PK, Raman R, Subramani S, Perumal G, Kumaramanickavel G, Sharma T. Knowledge of diabetes and diabetic retinopathy among rural populations in India, and the influence of knowledge of diabetic retinopathy on attitude and practice. *Rural and remote health*. 2008 Jul;8(3):1-9.
2. Tumosa N. Eye disease and the older diabetic. *Clinics in geriatric medicine*. 2008 Aug 1;24(3):515-27.
3. Jerneld B, Algreve P. Relationship of duration and onset of diabetes to prevalence of diabetic retinopathy. *American journal of ophthalmology*. 1986 Oct 1;102(4):431-7.
4. Yau JW, Rogers SL, Kawasaki R, Lamoureux EL, Kowalski JW, Bek T, Chen SJ, Dekker JM, Fletcher A, Grauslund J, Haffner S. Global prevalence and major risk factors of diabetic retinopathy. *Diabetes care*. 2012 Mar 1;35(3):556-64.
5. Aldahlawi A, Alamoudi L, Taher N, et al. (January 28, 2024) The Evaluation of Diabetic Patients' Awareness of Diabetic Retinopathy and Its Complications in the Western Region of Saudi Arabia. *Cureus* 16(1): e53090. DOI 10.7759/cureus.53090.

6. Khandekar R, Harby SA, Harthy HA, Lawatti JA: Knowledge, attitude and practice regarding eye complications and care among Omani persons with diabetes - a cross sectional study. *Oman J Ophthalmol.* 2010, 3:60-5. 10.4103/0974-620X.64228
7. Bakkar MM, Haddad MF, Gammoh YS: Awareness of diabetic retinopathy among patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus in Jordan. *Diabetes Metab Syndr Obes.* 2017, 10:435-41. 10.2147/DMSO.S140841
8. Cetin EN, Zencir M, Fenkçi S, Akın F, Yıldırım C: Assessment of awareness of diabetic retinopathy and utilization of eye care services among Turkish diabetic patients. *Prim Care Diabetes.* 2013, 7:297-302. 10.1016/j.pcd.2013.04.002
9. Albadrani M S, Alrehaili A M, Alahmadi S H, et al. (November 30, 2023) Awareness of Diabetic Retinopathy Among Patients With Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus in Primary Healthcare Centers in Madinah, Saudi Arabia: A Cross-Sectional Study. *Cureus* 15(11): e49718. DOI 10.7759/cureus.49718.